

Philosophical issues of quantum mechanics

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Abstract

In this paper we discuss some of the philosophy of quantum mechanics regarding a hidden fifth dimension and the symbols used to describe the metaphysical issues of this.

Keywords: hidden variables; Philosophy; quantum mechanics; Special relativity; General relativity

1. Introduction

In this paper apart from the equations we are going to discuss the symbolism behind quantum mechanics. On good point to start is the use of the annihilation and creation operators. The annihilation or destruction operator is alpha dagger. The dagger is one of the five holy items of the Sikh Hinduism. They all start from K. The talk is about the five dimensions that exist or as one may say the four because the fifth may be behind our reach.

As we have proved in our work[1-23] through discontinuities in ordinary spacetime and its curvature being a shadow of the five dimensions pairs of monopoles -antimonopoles appear as north and south. This is what the yin yang describes as dark (12 o clock midnight -the end) and light (12 noon midday). They describe the beginning and end of an event as seen by an observer.

We have five dimensions. The coordinate of the fifth axis is symbolized by X after which letter the X rays were named. The metric of the five dimensional world is symbolized by Y (yin-yang) and we put forth the following formula:

$$dY^2 = dX^2 + d\Omega^2 \quad (1)$$

In equation (1) Omega stands for the solid angles of the observer which are connected to the four dimensional spacetime metric

$$\Omega = K\tau \quad (2)$$

Another formula gives the curvature of space depending on the fine structure alpha and the Compton wavelength lambda:

$$K = \frac{\alpha}{\lambda_c} \quad (3)$$

The philosophy behind these two letters refers to the Ka , the soul in ancient Egypt which is symbolized by psichi in Greek.

Actually the fifth coordinate is the following:

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$$X = \frac{|\psi|}{K} \rightarrow X^2 = a^2 + b^2 \quad (4)$$

The new metric of our curved spacetime by the presence of mass is: $d\tau^2 = d\vec{r}^2 - \frac{c^2}{\chi} dt^2$ (5)

In equation (5) χ is the dielectric susceptibility χ :

$$\chi = \frac{N}{V} \quad (6)$$

The volume as witnessed by the observer is created from the five dimensional world. Actually V in Latin stands for five.

2. Conclusion

We have not found out whether the fifth dimension is imaginary purely but it connects the world of reality with some world we may not perceive. The philosophy was developed some 100 years ago mainly by German physicists. We hope we have contributed with this short paper. We would like to remind the reader that 2025 has been declared as the year of quantum for celebration of 100 years of this theory.

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